

Kinetics of Base Catalysed Iodination of Acetophenones

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The kinetics of iodination of acetophenone and its derivatives has been studied in various carboxylate buffers in 50% MeOH-H₂O v/v. The reaction was found to be first order in acetophenone and catalyst, and zero order in iodine. The activation parameters like $\Delta E^\ddagger$, $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ were evaluated. The Hammett reaction constants ' ρ ' were evaluated for different acids. The ionisation constants of different acids like propionic, acetic, lactic, glycollic and chloroacetic were determined experimentally in 50% MeOH-H₂O v/v at 35°. The catalytic constants in different buffers were measured at 35° for each acetophenone in 50% MeOH-H₂O. The Bronsted coefficients ' β ' were evaluated for each acetophenone and correlated with reaction constant ' ρ '.

EVEN though a detailed study on the halogenation of aliphatic and cyclic ketones was done by many workers¹⁻³, not much work seems to have been done on the halogenation of ketones using general base catalysis. A recent publication by Mhala et al⁴, has prompted us to publish our results.

In this communication we are presenting the work on iodination of acetophenone and substituted acetophenones in 50% MeOH with various carboxylate anions as catalysts with an aim to find the catalytic constants and also to correlate the reaction constant ' ρ ' with Bronsted coefficient ' β '.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Acetophenones were purified by known methods and the E-Merck quality methanol was distilled before use. An Elico pH-meter model L₁-10 was used for determining ionisation constants of the acids.

The reaction rate constants were measured in buffer solutions, prepared from NaOH (free from carbonate) and various carboxylic acid solutions in 50% MeOH-H₂O. The stock solutions of acetophenones in pure methanol and iodine in aqueous KI were prepared. The concentrations of acetophenone and I₂ were 0.05M and 0.005M respectively with varying buffer concentrations in the reaction mixture and the reaction was studied at a constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.6M$). The reaction at different temperatures (30-45°) with acetate buffer and at 35° with other buffers was followed by pipetting out aliquot portions of the reaction mixture into ice-cold water and excess iodine was titrated with standard thiosulfate. In all the cases pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated by the usual method. The error in rate constant was found to be about 3% and estimated error in $\Delta E^\ddagger$ was ± 0.8 k.cal.mole⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The rates of reaction were found to be first order in acetophenone, catalyst and zero order in iodine. The pseudo-first order rate constants at different temperatures and the activation parameters are given in Table 1. $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values are all negative and vary in a significant manner. The negative entropy values obtained for the activation process are indicative of a more rigid structure in the transition state than in the reactants.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE IODINATION OF ACETOPHENONES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES CATALYSED BY ACETATE BUFFER AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS AT 35° IN 50% MeOH-H₂O.

Aceto-phenone	Rate constant $k \times 10^3$ sec ⁻¹				$\Delta H^\ddagger$ k. cal. mole ⁻¹ E.u.	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$
	30°	35°	40°	45°		
H	1.15	1.59	3.22	5.25	18.8	19.4
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.55	4.34	7.39	12.13	19.6	14.9
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	14.70	26.86	50.66	82.61	21.1	6.5
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	23.96	44.86	77.96	137.40	21.9	1.4

Hammett Relationship: The rate constants for the reactions of each carboxylate anion with different acetophenones were correlated by the ' σ ' values gave a series of Hammett plots at 35° in 50% MeOH-H₂O as shown in Fig 1. The ' ρ ' values and thus the sensitivity of the reaction to the substituents in the aceto-

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Fig. 1. Hammett plots for the base catalysed iodination of acetophenones with different acids.

1. Propionic, 2. Acetic, 3. Lactic, 4. Glycolic and 5. Chloroacetic acid.

▲ - Acetophenone, □ - *p*-Cl-Acetophenone, ⊙ - *m*-NO₂-Acetophenone and ● - *p*-NO₂-Acetophenone.

phenones, depends on the basicity of acid (pK_a) as shown in Table 2. The ' ρ ' values are positive and increase with increase in pK_a of the acid.

TABLE 2—THE HAMMETT REACTION CONSTANT (ρ) FOR THE IODINATION OF ACETOPHENONES AND THE OBSERVED IONISATION CONSTANTS (pK_a) OF DIFFERENT ACIDS IN 50% MeOH-H₂O AT 35°

Acid	pK_a	ρ	*r
Propionic acid	5.65	1.77	0.9973
Acetic acid	5.37	1.66	0.9988
Lactic acid	4.57	1.06	0.9982
Glycolic acid	4.50	0.97	0.9996
Chloroacetic acid	3.65	0.57	0.9922

*Regression coefficient.

Bronsted Relationship: The catalytic constants of different buffers were calculated for each acetophenone by plotting observed rate constant against buffer salt concentration at a given pH in 50% MeOH-H₂O at 35° (Table 3). The ionisation constants of propionic, acetic, lactic, glycolic and chloroacetic acids were determined in 50% (v/v) MeOH-H₂O at 35°. The obtained data obeys the Bronsted equation. The plot of logarithm of catalytic constant versus pK_a of acid gave a series of Bronsted plots and the corresponding Bronsted slopes ' β ' are tabulated in Table 3. The Bronsted coefficient ' β ' provides a measure of the sensitivity of the reaction to the basicity of the acid and depends on the electron attracting power of the substituents in acetophenone. Table 3 indicates that as ' σ^- ' values increase from -H to *p*-NO₂, ' β ' values also increase.

Mechanism: The mechanism of the reaction of iodination of acetophenone with base (carboxylate

TABLE 3—CATALYTIC CONSTANTS OF DIFFERENT CARBOXYLATE BUFFERS AND THE BRONSTED COEFFICIENT ' β ' OF EACH ACETOPHENONE IN 50% MeOH-H₂O AT 35°.Acetophenone = 5×10^{-3} M ; Iodine = 5×10^{-3} M / $\mu = 0.6$ M

Acetophenone	β	ρ	Catalytic constant $k_a \times 10^5 M^{-1} \text{Sec}^{-1}$				
			Propionic	Acetic	Lactic	Glycolic	Chloroacetic
H	0.32	0.9978	6.25	4.90	2.95	2.82	1.41
<i>p</i> -Cl	0.47	0.9962	15.00	12.70	4.68	3.89	1.70
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.84	0.9856	104.50	67.61	13.40	11.22	2.29
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.88	0.9993	136.25	81.25	16.52	13.50	2.57

* Regression coefficient.

anion) as a catalyst can reasonably be formulated as a bimolecular nucleophilic attack of B⁻ (carboxylate anion) on carbonyl carbon. The effect of structural variations in carboxylate anion and in acetophenone is apparent from Hammett and Bronsted plots. The ' ρ ' values obtained are positive ranging from 0.57 to 1.77 (Table 2.), indicating that the presence of electron-attracting groups in the ring favours the nucleophilic attack at carbonyl carbon, because of the decrease in electron density at the reaction centre. The Bronsted slopes ' β ' obtained are in the range of 0.32 to 0.88. A high β value (near to 1.0) indicates a high degree of proton transfer to the catalysing base in the transition state and a low value indicates a low degree of proton transfer⁵. The order of reactivity of the acetophenones from Bronsted slopes confirmed as *p*-NO₂ > *m*-NO₂ > *p*-Cl > H. The ' β ' and ' ρ ' values are not equal but show a regular variation. This can be understood in terms of changes in bond formation B...C at carbonyl carbon and bond breaking C...H in methyl group adjacent to carboxyl carbon, in the transition state with the changes in electron withdrawing ability of the substituents⁶.

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